

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_type2_d_Topo		
Created on:	4/12/2021 4:50:04 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	25.15	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.3837	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...0x_type2_d_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/12/2021 4:50:04 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	9.761	μm	
Min:	-5.121	μm	
Max:	4.640	μm	
Size:	254383	digits	
Spacing:	0.03837	nm	
NM-points ratio:	5.923 % (533084 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/12/2021 4:50:04 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis: X			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis: Y			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis: Z			
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	9.761	μm	
Size:	254383	digits	
Spacing:	0.03837	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	1.308	μm	
Ssk	-0.3805		
Sku	5.155		
Sp	4.636	μm	
Sv	5.125	μm	
Sz	9.761	μm	
Sa	0.9382	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	1.069	%	
Smc	1.506	μm	
Sxp	3.082	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	21.39	μm	
Str	0.1794		
Std	25.50	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.1999		
Sdr	1.844	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.06915	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	1.575	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.06915	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.9309	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	1.368	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.2070	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	4.177	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.8795	µm
Mean density of furrows	3686	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	26.42	°
Second direction	180.0	°
Third direction	45.03	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	14.62	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

